

Supplementary File 11: Time Series of Cardiorespiratory Measures

Figure S1

Heart Rate Data

Note. Heart rate during warm up and for each 2.5-min interval, in each condition. Each color represents an individual participant. WU = warm up.

Figure S2

Respiratory Rate Data

Note. Respiratory rate during warm up and for each 2.5-min interval, in each condition. Each color represents an individual participant. WU = warm up.